

**New species and new records of ichneumon wasps from Africa
(Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae, Cryptinae, Ophioninae)**

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Abstract – Afrotropical and Palearctic species of the subfamilies Campopleginae, Cryptinae and Ophioninae of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) are treated. *Hyposoter ardens* sp. nov. and *Xanthocampoplex melanocephalus* sp. nov. are described from South Africa. An identification key to the Afrotropical species of *Xanthocampoplex* Morley, 1913 is provided. *Hyposoter obliquus* (Seyrig, 1935) is reported for the first time from South Africa, *Meloboris collector* (Thunberg, 1822), *Bathyplectes carinatus* Horstmann, 1974 and *B. nigridens* (Horstmann, 1980) from Tunisia, the latter with the description of the hitherto unknown male. *Coccygodes bifasciatus* (Cameron, 1912), *Gabunia coerulea* Kriechbaumer, 1895 and *Osprynchotus objurgator* (Fabricius, 1781) are reported for the first time from Liberia, *Enicospilus babaulti* (Seyrig, 1935) and *E. bicoloratus* Cameron, 1912 from Tanzania, *E. biimpressus* (Brullé, 1846) from Kenya, *E. brevicornis* (Masi, 1939) from Tanzania, *E. equatus* Gauld et Mitchell, 1978 from Rwanda, *E. glyphanosus* Gauld et Mitchell, 1978 from the Republic of Congo, *E. grandiflavus* Townes, 1973 from Tanzania, *E. helvolus* Gauld et Mitchell, 1978 from Cameroon and Ethiopia, *E. lancasteri* Gauld et Mitchell, 1978 from Liberia, *E. lictus* Gauld et Mitchell, 1978 from Tanzania, *E. marjorieae* Gauld et Mitchell, 1978 from Rwanda, *E. prolixus* Gauld et Mitchell, 1978 from Cameroon, *E. quietus* (Seyrig, 1935) from Ghana, *Dicamptus bantu* Delobel, 1976 from Eritrea, and *Euryophion titanius* Vas, 2022 from Cameroon, the latter with the description of the hitherto unknown male.

Key words – taxonomy, species description, identification key, distribution, biogeography, Afrotropical region, Palearctic region

INTRODUCTION

Identification of the African Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) material of the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest (HNHM) and the Biological Museum of Lund University, Lund (MZLU) resulted in two new species and several new faunistic records, which are presented in this paper. The biogeographical scope covers continental Africa and adjacent islands, including the entire Afrotropical region, as well as the North African area of the Western

Palaeartic. Taxonomy and nomenclature follow YU *et al.* (2016). Morphological terminology follows GAULD (1991) and GAULD *et al.* (1997); however, in the cases of wing veins the corresponding terminology of TOWNES (1969) is also indicated. Identifications were based on KIRBY (1896), CAMERON (1905, 1906, 1912), SZÉPLIGETI (1906, 1908), KRIEGER (1911), MORLEY (1912, 1914, 1917, 1926), GHIGI (1915), SEYRIG (1935), ROMAN (1943), WALLEY (1944), BENOIT (1957), GUPTA & GUPTA (1971), GUPTA (1973), DELOBEL (1976), HORSTMANN (1974, 1980), GAULD & MITCHELL (1978), ROUSSE & VILLEMANT (2012), ROUSSE & VAN NOORT (2014), WATANABE (2019), VAS (2021, 2022), VAN NOORT (2022), and on examination of adequate type materials (at least from photos of scientific quality). The specimens were identified by the author using a Nikon SMZ645 stereoscopic microscope. Label data of type specimens are given verbatim, with additions and explanations in square brackets if necessary. Taxa are listed alphabetically.

RESULTS

Campopleginae

Bathyplectes carinatus Horstmann, 1974

Material examined – Tunisia: 25 km SW of Bizerte, 10.IV.1994, leg. R. Danielsson, 2 females; 12 km E of Mateur, 12.IV.1994, same collector, 1 female, 2 males. Deposited in MZLU, except one female in HNHM.

Remarks – First records for Tunisia. This species is known from several European countries (YU *et al.* 2016); the present records represent its first report from the Western Palaeartic part of Africa.

Bathyplectes nigridens (Horstmann, 1980)

Material examined – Tunisia: 17 km SE of Zaghuane, 7.IV.1994, leg. R. Danielsson, 1 male; 1 km S of Tabarka, 8.IV.1994, same collector, 4 females; 8 km S of Tabarka, 8.IV.1994, same collector, 1 female; 4 km E of Ain Sebaa, 23 km E of Tabarka, 9.IV.1994, same collector, 1 female; N of Sousse, 3 km S of Hergla, 12.IV.1994, same collector, 1 female. Deposited in MZLU, except one female in HNHM.

Remarks – First records for Tunisia. This species was known from Spain only (HORSTMANN 1980, YU *et al.* 2016).

Complementary description – The species was described based on a single female specimen (HORSTMANN 1980). The male is similar to the female, it mostly agrees with the character states given in the original description (HORSTMANN 1980), except its antenna having 22 flagellomeres, body length of ca. 5 mm, and its mandible being medially brownish (the latter character state was also observed in some females).

***Hyposoter ardens* sp. nov.**

(Figs 1–2)

Type material – Holotype: female, “S. Afr. [= South Africa], Cape Prov. [= Province], Cape Peninsula, Hout Bay, Skoorsteenkop, 26.XII.[19]50, No. 95, Swedish South Africa Expedition 1950–1951, Brunck – Rudebeck, Insect trap”; specimen pinned, id. MZLU 00172984. Holotype is deposited in MZLU.

Diagnosis – The new species can be easily identified among the Afrotropical species of *Hyposoter* Förster, 1869 by the following character states in combination: propodeal carinae anterior to level of costulae (including costulae) strong, posterior to level of costulae weak; area basalis narrowly triangular, its tip merging into a single longitudinal carina before joining area superomedia; area superomedia pentagonal, ca. 1.5× as long as wide, posteriorly opened; ovipositor straight; mesosoma reddish orange with black patches; metasoma reddish orange except tergites 1–2 and basal half of tergite 3 predominantly black; hind coxa and hind femur orange, hind tibia orange-brown, medially paler.

Description – Female (Figs 1–2). Body length ca. 5.5 mm, fore wing length ca. 4 mm.

Head: Antenna with 31 flagellomeres; first flagellomere long and slender, ca. 4× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres slightly longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate, without punctures; hairs dense and short, on face and clypeus slightly longer. Ocular-ocellar distance 1.1× as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 1.5× as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits weakly indented, subparallel. Gena moderately short and strongly, roundly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.5× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, slightly elevated, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, weakly impressed above toruli. Face and clypeus weakly convex in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, moderately small, its apical margin weakly convex, sharp. Malar space 0.7× as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible moderately short and wide, lower margin with rather wide flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly wider than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma relatively elongate, matt, granulate without punctures, and with short to moderately long, dense hairs. Pronotum with

transverse wrinkles on lower half, epomia indistinct. Mesoscutum little longer than wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide, relatively shallow. Scutellum convex in profile, lateral carina not developed. Mesopleuron granulate with weak wrinkles anterior to speculum, speculum very finely granulate, matt. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it above its middle height, ventral part (behind fore coxae) not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, relatively weak, not elevated. Metanotum $0.4\times$ as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum strong; propodeal spiracle small, circular, separated from pleural carina by about its length, connected to pleural carina by a distinct ridge. Propodeum short, convex in profile, granulate, posterior two-thirds with transverse wrinkles; anterior transverse carina and longitudinal carinae anterior to level of costulae strongly developed, posterior transverse carina and longitudinal carinae posterior to level of costulae weak but discernible. Area basalis elongate, narrowly triangular, its bordering lateral carinae apically merging into a single longitudinal carina before joining area superomedia. Area superomedia pentagonal, ca. $1.5\times$ as long as wide, posteriorly opened, its lateral sides subparallel behind costulae. Area petiolaris confluent with area superomedia, relatively short, posteriorly widened. Fore wing with petiolate, rectangular areolet, *3rs-m* present, pigmented, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) close to distal corner of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* straight; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by $0.2\times$ its length, vertical; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted distinctly below its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) slightly reclinous, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae granulate. Hind femur ca. $4.7\times$ as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. $0.5\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma relatively short, weakly compressed, finely granulate to shagreened with weak, indistinct traces of punctures, and with dense, short hairs. First tergite ca. $3\times$ as long as its apical width, $1.3\times$ as long as second tergite, glymma strong. Second tergite $1.2\times$ as long as its apical width; thyridium moderately large, oval, about as long as its distance from basal margin of tergite. Posterior margins of apical tergites medially not excised. Ovipositor sheath slightly longer than apical depth of metasoma; ovipositor strong, straight.

Colour: Antenna dark brown except scapus and pedicellus ventrally brownish yellow. Head black, except palpi and mandible yellowish, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma reddish orange with black patches; black patches present on lower two-thirds of pronotum, anterior parts of mesosternum, around sutures, and forming a posterior black band on propodeum and a black triangle on mesoscutum anterior to scutellum; tegula pale yellowish. Metasoma: tergites

1–2 and basal half of tergite 3 predominantly black, from apical half of tergite 3 on reddish orange; ovipositor sheath dark brown. Wings hyaline, wing veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs: coxae, trochanters and trochantelli ivory; femora, tibiae and tarsi light orange. Hind leg: coxa orange; trochanter brownish orange; trochantellus ivory; femur orange; tibia orange-brown, medially somewhat paler; tarsus brownish.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – South Africa.

Etymology – The specific epithet *ardens* is a Latin one-termination participle treated as an adjective, meaning glowing, flaming, fiery; it refers to the extensive reddish colouration of the new species.

Remarks on identification – Due to its colouration, the new species is somewhat similar to *Hyposoter nanodraco* Vas, 2021, also described from South Africa. However, in the latter species the propodeal carinae are absent (except a very weak, short, barely discernible trace of median section of anterior transverse carina), fore wings are conspicuously long (almost as long as body), and the reddish orange coloration is less extensive (pronotum, mesopleuron and metapleuron entirely, clypeus, scutellum, metanotum, hind coxa partly orange).

Figs 1–2. *Hyposoter ardens* sp. nov., holotype, 1 = habitus, 2 = propodeum (photo by Zoltán Vas, drawing by Viktória Szőke)

Hyposoter obliquus (Seyrig, 1935)

Material – South Africa: Cape Province, Cape Peninsula, Hout Bay, Skoorsteenkop, 22.I.1951, No. 157, Swedish South Africa Expedition 1950–1951, leg. Brunck & Rudebeck, 2 females; same locality and collectors, 2.II.1951, No. 166, 2 females. Deposited in MZLU, except one female in HNHM.

Remarks – First records for South Africa. This species was known from Kenya only (SEYRIG 1935, YU *et al.* 2016).

Meloboris collector (Thunberg, 1822)

Material examined – Tunisia: 25 km SW of Bizerte, 10.IV.1994, leg. R. Danielsson, 1 female; N of Sousse, 3 km S of Hergla, 12.IV.1994, same collector, 1 female. Deposited in MZLU.

Remarks – First records for Tunisia. This species is widespread in the Palaearctic and Afrotropical regions (YU *et al.* 2016).

Xanthocampoplex melanocephalus sp. nov.

(Figs 3–4)

Type material – Holotype: female, “S. Afr. [= South Africa], Cape Prov. [= Province], Hout Bay, Skoorsteenkop, 22.I.[19]51, No. 157, Swedish South Africa Expedition 1950–1951, Brunck – Rudebeck, Insect trap”; specimen pinned, id. MZLU 00172985. Holotype is deposited in MZLU.

Diagnosis – The new species can be identified by the following character states in combination: head granulate without punctures; malar space 0.8× as long as basal width of mandible; mesosoma entirely granulate with indistinct, superficial punctures on lower half of mesopleuron and on metapleuron; propodeal spiracle circular; propodeum long, very weakly convex in profile, medially not impressed, entirely granulate without transverse wrinkles or rugosity, propodeal carinae not developed except the weak anterior transverse carina; fore wing with short-stalked, relatively large areolet; head black except clypeus orange; mesosoma light orange, mesoscutum with a brownish median longitudinal stripe; metasoma light orange; legs light orange, except apical tarsomeres more or less brownish.

Description – Female (Figs 3–4). Body length ca. 9 mm, fore wing length ca. 6 mm.

Head: Antenna with 41 flagellomeres; first flagellomere long and slender, ca. 4× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres distinctly longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, granulate, without punctures; hairs dense and moderately short, on face and clypeus little longer. Ocular-ocellar distance 1.2× as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits weakly indented, slightly convergent ventrad. Gena moderately short and strongly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.4× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina before base of mandible. Frons flat, weakly impressed above toruli. Face and clypeus almost flat in profile, clypeus very weakly separated from face, moderately small, its apical margin weakly, evenly convex, sharp. Malar space 0.8× as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible moderately short and wide, lower margin with wide flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely, moderately abruptly narrowed at teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly longer and wider than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma relatively elongate, matt, entirely granulate with some indistinct, small and superficial punctures on lower half of mesopleuron and on metapleuron, and with short, dense hairs. Pronotum with weak transverse wrinkles on lower half, epomia not developed. Mesoscutum slightly longer than wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide, relatively shallow. Scutellum convex in profile, lateral carina not developed except very shortly at extreme base. Speculum finely granulate, matt. Epicnemial carina complete, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it above its middle height, ventral part (behind fore coxae) not elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, slightly elevated. Metanotum $0.4\times$ as long as scutellum. Metapleuron without juxtacoxal carina; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum strong; propodeal spiracle circular, separated from pleural carina by less than its length, connected to pleural carina by a distinct ridge. Propodeum relatively long, very weakly convex in profile, medially not impressed, entirely granulate without transverse wrinkles or rugosity. Propodeal carinae not developed, except the weak anterior transverse carina, and short, inconspicuous traces of longitudinal carinae at extreme apex; propodeal areas not defined. Fore wing with short-stalked, relatively large, rectangular areolet, *3rs-m* present, pigmented, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) distal to middle of areolet; distal abscissa of *Rs* straight, at extreme distal part weakly curved towards wing margin; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by ca. $0.15\times$ its length, vertical; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a + Cu1b*) intercepted slightly below its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell acute. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a + abscissa of Cu1 between M and cu-a*) slightly reclivous, almost vertical, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus. Coxae finely granulate with indistinct, superficial punctures. Hind femur slender, ca. $6.3\times$ as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia ca. $0.6\times$ as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Hind basitarsus with a midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs. Tarsal claws small, thin, little shorter than arolium, pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma moderately compressed, finely granulate to shagreened, with dense, short hairs. First tergite slender, subterete, $4\times$ as long as its apical width, $1.4\times$ as long as second tergite, glymma small and shallow. Second tergite $1.5\times$ as long as its apical width; thyridium elongate oval, about as long as its distance from basal margin of tergite. Posterior margins of apical tergites medially not excised. Ovipositor sheath slightly longer than apical depth of metasoma; ovipositor straight.

Colour: Antenna dark brown except scapus and pedicellus ventrally yellowish orange. Head black, except clypeus orange, palpi and mandible yellowish, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma light orange, mesoscutum with a brownish median longitudinal stripe; tegula yellowish. Metasoma light orange; ovipositor sheath dark brown. Wings hyaline, wing veins and pterostigma

brown. Legs, including coxae, light orange, except apical tarsomeres more or less brownish.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – South Africa.

Etyymology – The specific epithet *melanocephalus* is the masculine form of the Latinised Greek adjective *melanocephalus*, *-a*, *-um*, meaning black-headed; it refers to the colouration of the new species.

Remarks on identification – The new species is somewhat similar to *Xanthocampoplex oneili* (Cameron, 1905). They can be easily distinguished with the identification key to the Afrotropical species of *Xanthocampoplex* Morley, 1913 provided below. Supporting but not distinguishing character states are given in parentheses, distributional data in square brackets.

- 1 Propodeal carinae strongly developed, longitudinal carinae also distinct and strong posterior to the level of costulae, propodeal areas clearly defined; areolet very small, distinctly shorter than its stalk (head yellow with only ocellar area black; propodeum rather coarsely rugose, medially distinctly impressed) [Réunion]
..... *Xanthocampoplex huberti* Rouse et Villemant, 2012
- Propodeal carinae reduced, anterior transverse carina present but longitudinal carinae absent or obsolete, propodeal areas not or not clearly defined; areolet relatively large, distinctly longer than its stalk 2
- 2 Head black except clypeus orange; propodeal spiracle circular; propodeum relatively long, very weakly convex in profile, medially not impressed, entirely granulate without transverse wrinkles or rugosity; face and clypeus entirely granulate without punctures [South Africa] .
..... *Xanthocampoplex melanocephalus* sp. nov.
- Head yellow with only ocellar area black; propodeal spiracle elongate linear; propodeum short, convex in profile, medially impressed, with transverse wrinkles or rugosity; face and clypeus punctate-reticulate [South Africa and Kenya]
..... *Xanthocampoplex oneili* (Cameron, 1905)

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Figs 3–4. *Xanthocampoplex melanocephalus* sp. nov., holotype, 1 = habitus, 2 = propodeum (photo by Zoltán Vas, drawing by Viktória Szóke)

Cryptinae

Coccygodes bifasciatus (Cameron, 1912)

Material examined – Liberia: Nimba Mountains, Gbarpa, Gba Community Forest, 7°25'47"N, 8°38'53"W, 500m, 28.IV.–5.V.2021, leg. Sz. Sáfián, 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Liberia. This species was known from the Democratic Republic of Congo only (YU *et al.* 2016).

Gabunia coerulea Kriechbaumer, 1895

Material examined – Liberia: Nimba Mountains, Glassfield FDA office, 7°29'31"N, 8°34'54"W, 493m, 10–21.IV.2021, leg. Sz. Sáfián, 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Liberia. This species is known from several countries of Middle and West Africa (YU *et al.* 2016).

Osprynchotus objurgator (Fabricius, 1781)

Material examined – Liberia: Nimba Mountains, Glassfield FDA office, 7°29'31"N, 8°34'54"W, 493m, 28.IV.–5.V.2021, leg. Sz. Sáfián, 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Liberia. This species is known from several countries of North, Middle and West Africa (YU *et al.* 2016).

Ophioninae

Dicamptus bantu Delobel, 1976

Material examined – Eritrea: Ghinda, 15.IX.–25.X.1966, leg. K. Ferencz, 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Eritrea. This species was described from the Central African Republic and is known from Angola, Democratic Republic of Congo, Nigeria, Uganda, and Guinea (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016, VAS 2022). The new record represents its easternmost locality in Africa.

Enicospilus babaulti (Seyrig, 1935)

Material examined – Tanzania: W Usambara Mts., Mazumbai University Forest Reserve, 1500m, 18.II.1985, leg. L. Peregovits, 1 male. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Tanzania. This species is widespread in the Afrotropical region (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus bicoloratus Cameron, 1912

Material examined – Tanzania: Monogoro, II.1970, leg. T. Pócs, 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Tanzania. This species is widely distributed in the Afrotropical region (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus biimpressus (Brullé, 1846)

Material examined – Kenya: Mt. Elgon Nat. P., near Chepnyalil Cave, dry evergreen montane forest, 2500m, 24–28.I.1992, leg. O. Merkl & G. Várkonyi, at light, 1 male. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Kenya. This species is widely distributed in the Afrotropical region (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus brevicornis (Masi, 1939)

Material examined – Tanzania: Arusha-Ju, 1906, leg. Katona [=K. Kittenberger], 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Tanzania. This species is widely distributed in the Afrotropical region, and also occurs in the northern, Western Palaearctic part of Africa (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus equatus Gauld et Mitchell, 1978

Material examined – Rwanda: Volcanoes Nat. P., 4.V.1988, leg. A. Vojnits (Hung. Sci. Africa Exp. “Teleki”), light trap, 1 male. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Rwanda. This species is widely distributed in Middle and East Africa (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus glyphanosus Gauld et Mitchell, 1978

Material examined – Congo: Brazzaville-Congo, Mt Foari Reservatum, 12.XII.1963, leg. J. Balog & A. Zicsi, 1 male. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for the Republic of Congo. This species was known from Angola, Democratic Republic of Congo, Nigeria and Uganda (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus grandiflavus Townes, 1973

Material examined – Tanzania: W Usambara Mts., Mazumbai University Field Station, 1520m, 9.II.1985, leg. L. Peregovits, 1 female; W Usambara Mts., Shume Forestry Guesthouse, 1920m, 14.II.1985, leg. L. Peregovits, 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First records for Tanzania. This species is known from Middle and South Africa, and from Madagascar and Réunion (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus helvolus Gauld et Mitchell, 1978

Material examined – Cameroon: Middle Cameroon, 14.II.1913, leg. unknown, 1 male. Ethiopia: 8 km S of Dessie, 19.IX.1980, leg. A. Demeter (No. 17), 1 male. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First records for Cameroon and Ethiopia. This species is known from West, East and South Africa, and from Réunion (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus lancasteri Gauld et Mitchell, 1978

Material examined – Liberia: Nimba Mountains, Gbarpa, Gba Community Forest, 7°25'47"N, 8°38'53"W, 500m, 28.IV.–5.V.2021, leg. Sz. Sáfián, 2 males. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Liberia. This species was known from Democratic Republic of Congo, Nigeria and Uganda (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016). The new record represents its westernmost locality in Africa.

Enicospilus lictus Gauld et Mitchell, 1978

Material examined – Tanzania: W Usambara Mts., Mazumbai University Field Station, 1520m, 25.I.1985, leg. L. Peregovits, 1 male. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Tanzania. This species is known from West, East and Middle Africa (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus marjorieae Gauld et Mitchell, 1978

Material examined – Rwanda: Kagera Nat. P., 1.V.1988, leg. A. Vojnits (Hung. Sci. Africa Exp. “Teleki”), light trap, 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Rwanda. This species was known from South Africa only (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016), the new record represents its northernmost locality in the Afrotropical region.

Enicospilus prolixus Gauld et Mitchell, 1978

Material examined – Cameroon: Abong Mbang, 1985, leg. R. Lenczy, 1 male. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Cameroon. This species is widely distributed in the Afrotropical region (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus quietus (Seyrig, 1935)

Material examined – Ghana: Northern region, Damogo, 9°4'N, 1°48'W, 220m, 11.XI.1970, leg. S. Endrődy-Younga, light trap, No. 440, 1 female. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Ghana. This species is widely distributed in Middle, East and South Africa (GAULD & MITCHELL 1978, YU *et al.* 2016). The new record represents its westernmost locality.

Euryophion titanius Vas, 2022

Material examined – Cameroon: Yaoundé, 4–12.XI.2012, leg. Gy. Hangay, 1 male. Deposited in HNHM.

Remarks – First record for Cameroon. This species was recently described from Liberia and the Republic of Congo (VAS 2022).

Complementary description – The species was described based on females (VAS 2022). The male is rather similar to female, agrees with the character states given in the original description (VAS 2022), except its first flagellomere is slightly stouter, 1.6× as long as second flagellomere, and its propodeal carinae are more strongly developed.

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